

What potential does the EU Single-Use Plastics Directive have for reducing plastic pollution at coastlines and riversides? An evaluation based on citizen science data

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Single-use plastics
Plastic pollution
Citizen science
EU legislation
EU Directive 2019/904

ABSTRACT

To address environmental pollution by plastic litter, the European Union adopted EU Directive 2019/904, the so called “Single-Use Plastics Directive” (SUPD), which bans several single-use plastic products and addresses additional items with measures such as extended producer responsibility and obligatory requirements for product redesign. This study assessed the potential of the SUPD to reduce litter pollution in the environment with three scenarios. The “best case” scenario assumed that all measures of the SUPD completely prevent targeted items from getting into the environment. Another scenario assumed that no measures besides bans were effective. An intermediate scenario assumed partial effectiveness of measures. Data of almost 5,000 sampling events from citizen science protocols (Plastic Pirates, International Coastal Cleanup, Marine Litter Watch) and the OSPAR protocol were used to analyse litter at riversides and coastlines in Germany and the European Union. 44 to 68% of litter items in citizen science protocols consisted of single-use plastics (cigarette butts were the most prominent items). At coastlines sampled by the OSPAR protocol, fishing gear and undefined plastics prevailed. The scenario analysis revealed that substantial litter reductions could be achieved in the “best case” scenario (upwards of 40%), while the intermediate scenario resulted in litter reductions of 13 to 25%. The marginal effect of the “only bans” scenario achieved a reduction of 2–6% in Germany and the European Union, respectively. Thus, depending on implementation and enforcement, the current SUPD can be an important first step, yet further legislative actions are needed to effectively prevent plastic waste pollution.

1. Introduction

Plastics have become ubiquitous pollutants in many environments. Plastic litter and particles pollute the ocean, rivers, urban environments, as well as remote habitats (see e.g. Chiba et al., 2018, Brahney et al., 2020, Lechner, 2020, Qiu et al., 2020). This affects the health and well-being of animals and humans alike (Groh et al., 2019, Parthasarathy et al., 2019, Green, 2020, Kühn and van Franeker 2020). In addition, it causes significant costs to different sectors of the economy, such as fisheries, aquaculture, shipping, and tourism (Beaumont et al., 2019,

Aretoulaki et al., 2021). No other way of using this material represents the problem of plastic pollution as much as single-use plastics (SUPs). A SUP product is “a product that is made wholly or partly from plastic and that is not conceived, designed or placed on the market to accomplish, within its life span, multiple trips or rotations by being returned to a producer for refill or re-used for the same purpose for which it was conceived” (EU Directive 2019/904).

SUPs have become a particular problem due to (i) their very short life span (often they are discarded after only minutes of use, completely undermining the benefits of one of the key properties of plastics, their

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.03.042>

Received 25 October 2022; Received in revised form 15 March 2023; Accepted 28 March 2023

Available online 10 April 2023

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longevity), (ii) their ubiquity (SUPs are the most common type of plastics produced, [Chen et al., 2021](#)), and (iii) the difficulty to recycle SUPs ([Geyer et al., 2017](#), [Eriksen et al., 2019](#), [Chen et al., 2021](#)). As a consequence, SUPs such as shopping bags, beverage containers, wrappers, sachets, and plastic bottles frequently end up in different aquatic environments ([Morales-Caselles et al., 2021](#)), and also represent a large proportion of litter found in rivers and along river shores ([Morritt et al., 2014](#), [Blettler et al., 2017](#), [Schöneich-Argent et al., 2020](#), [Mitchell et al., 2021](#)).

Measures to address this problem include, for example, the introduction of bans or levies on certain products ([Taylor and Villas-Boas, 2016](#), [Heidbreder et al., 2019](#), [Nielsen et al., 2019](#)), deposit-refund systems ([Zhou et al., 2020](#), [Calabrese et al., 2021](#)), extended producer responsibility schemes ([Watkins et al., 2017](#), [Rubio et al., 2019](#), [Bassi et al., 2020](#)), and education and information campaigns targeting consumers ([Wagner, 2017](#), [Heidbreder et al., 2019](#), [Wagner, 2020](#), [Borg et al., 2022](#)). Considering individual items, legislation has been adopted most prominently against SUP bags: they are banned in many countries of the Global South, while a levy is charged in most European countries ([Xanthos and Walker, 2017](#), [Knoblauch et al., 2018](#), [Nielsen et al., 2019](#), [Adam et al., 2020](#), [Cristi et al., 2020](#), [Adeyanju et al., 2021](#)). Other SUPs are targeted less frequently by legislation, but the number is growing. In 2018, 27 countries had enacted some type of ban on other types of SUPs, for example on plastic plates, cups, and straws or products made from expanded polystyrene ([Schnurr et al., 2018](#)). As an example, Canada has recently adopted extensive legislation that includes bans for some SUPs (e.g. plastic cutlery, straws, and ring carriers for beverages) and declared manufactured plastic items as toxic substances (i.e. substances with an immediate or long-term harmful effect on the environment; [Canadian Government, 2021a, 2021b, 2021c](#)); this decision has resulted in major push backs from the plastics industry, including attempts to sue the Canadian government ([Walker, 2021](#)).

To address environmental pollution by SUPs and fishing gear in the European Union, [EU Directive 2019/904](#) (hereafter SUPD) has been introduced. This legislation is intended to promote the transition to a circular economy and was adopted following the publication of the EU Plastic Strategy in 2018 ([European Commission, 2018a](#); see [Elliott et al., 2020](#)) for developments leading towards the SUPD). The SUPD focuses on ten groups of SUPs (among them cutlery, plates, and straws, food and beverage containers, balloons and sticks for balloons, cigarettes, plastic bags, plastic wrapping, wet wipes, and sanitary items) as well as fishing gear containing plastic. These items have been identified to be among the most common litter objects found on European beaches through an evaluation of available data from 2016 ([Addamo et al., 2017](#)). The SUPD contains a mix of measures, e.g. banning certain SUPs (such as plastic cutlery and plates, as well as cotton buds with a plastic rod), and introducing extended producer responsibility measures, mandatory labelling, and product design requirements ([Table 1](#)); the SUPD treats “bioplastics” in the same way as conventional plastics.

The global plastic pollution problem is predicted to increase in scale (see e.g. [Eriksen et al., 2023](#)) and impact, despite legislative action by governments around the world ([Borrelle et al., 2020](#), [Lau et al., 2020](#)). As only certain SUPs are being covered by the SUPD, it becomes imperative to estimate the potential effectiveness of these measures in reducing the fraction of plastic litter in the environment and identify shortcomings of the legislation. To do so, we (i) analysed and compared the current proportions of litter items and especially SUPs at riversides and coastlines in Germany and coastlines in the European Union, and (ii) evaluated whether the SUPD could significantly contribute to the reduction of plastic pollution, based on three scenarios making assumptions about the effectiveness of measures in reducing litter quantities in the environment. These assumptions have their limitations (e.g. they do not reflect the replacement of SUPs by other single-use items, which could be frequently littered), and the scenarios present a current estimate of the potential of all measures of the SUPD to reduce environmental litter pollution. The analysis is based on large-scale data

Table 1

Overview of measures from [EU Directive 2019/904](#) for addressed products and details on how litter items were matched to the Directive in the present study. Some of the products were not investigated (due to a lack of data in the four considered sampling protocols) while other products were only considered partially or in a broader sense (see details below the table). EPR = Extended producer responsibility.

Product addressed by the EU Directive 2019/904	Measure of EU Directive 2019/904	Litter category in the present study
Plastic bags (lightweight carrier bags)	EPR, Awareness raising	Plastic bags ^[1]
Plastic beverage containers/bottles including caps and lids	Product design requirements, EPR, Collection target, Awareness raising	Plastic bottles for beverages Plastic lids of beverage bottles
Plastic cups for beverages (including covers and lids)	Reduction of consumption, Labelling of products, EPR, Awareness raising	Takeaway and fast food packaging (incl. disposable coffee cups and lids), made from expanded polystyrene and other plastics ^[2]
Expanded polystyrene cups/containers for beverages (including covers and lids)	Market restriction/ban	
Plastic take-away and fast-food containers	Reduction of consumption, EPR, Awareness raising	
Expanded polystyrene take-away and fast food containers	Market restriction/ban	
Plastic cutlery, including beverage stirrers, straws and plates	Market restriction/ban	Plastic cutlery and plastic plates (incl. plastic coffee stirrers and plastic straws)
Plastic packets and wrappers made from flexible material for foods for immediate consumption	EPR, Awareness raising	Plastic packaging for sweets, crisps, etc.
Cotton buds with plastic rod	Market restriction/ban	Cotton buds with plastic rod
Sanitary towels, tampons, and tampon applicators	Labelling of products, Awareness raising	Wet wipes, tampons and sanitary towels ^[3]
Wet wipes	Labelling of products, EPR, Awareness raising	
Balloons (consumer balloons)	EPR, Awareness raising	Balloons
Balloon sticks	Market restriction/ban	na ^[4]
Tobacco products with filters or filters for tobacco products	Labelling of products, EPR, Awareness raising	Cigarette butts
Fishing gear containing plastic	EPR, Collection target	Plastic fishing gear

^[1]The Directive addresses lightweight carrier bags, while in the present study all types of plastic bags (also those not originating from grocery shopping) are included.

^[2]These litter items were grouped as two protocols do not report them separately.

^[3]Tampon applicators were not considered in the present study.

^[4]Balloon sticks were not considered in the present study.

collected by three citizen science programs, the Plastic Pirates (investigating riverside litter, [Kiessling et al., 2019](#), [Kiessling et al., 2021](#)), the International Coastal Cleanup (ICC) and Marine Litter Watch (MLW; both focusing on litter from coastlines; [Ocean Conservancy, 2022](#), [EEA, 2022](#)) and data from the OSPAR protocol (an agreement to protect the North-East Atlantic based on the Oslo and Paris Conventions, likewise collecting litter data from coastlines; [OSPAR Commission, 2010](#)). These

datasets (mostly open access and collected by volunteers) were invaluable to the present study.

2. Methods

2.1. Litter data

2.1.1. Sampling of litter at riversides

Litter at riversides in Germany was sampled as part of the citizen science project Plastic Pirates, engaging young people in research on the plastic pollution problem (Kiessling et al., 2019, 2021). For the present study, litter data from five sampling campaigns was used (May to July of 2019, 2020, and 2021, as well as September to November of 2020 and 2021), collected by more than 8,000 schoolchildren and other participants from more than 350 schools and youth organisations ([Supplemental material 1](#)).

At the riverside, the participants established a sorting station for litter objects, consisting of different categories for plastics (including ten categories of SUPs), metals, glass items, and other waste ([Supplemental material 2](#)). Subsequently litter was collected at the riverside within 20 m of the river itself, and counted into buckets of the sorting station. The lateral distance covered depended on the capacity of the participants and was recorded by each group. Participants were instructed to submit photos of their litter findings, along with the data, to the coordinating laboratory (Kiel Science Factory) to corroborate their findings. The sampling method was detailed in a booklet available to each participant at no cost ([Supplemental material 3](#)).

A total of 439 groups conducted the sampling, but 33 of those 439 groups did not hand in data or submitted illegible data. Data from another 16 groups had to be excluded from the analysis, mostly because the sampling instructions were not followed precisely (e.g. litter was weighted and not counted, litter was only partially quantified, or other litter categories were used), and data from 11 groups were excluded because no coordinates of the sampling site were submitted or the sampling site was not located in Germany. This resulted in 379 groups for which data could be analysed. Some school groups participated several times in subsequent samplings, and they were counted independently for each of the five sampling campaigns in which they participated. In each individual sampling event, litter items were registered.

To corroborate the data from the 379 sampling events, photos submitted by 195 groups were compared to values annotated on the datasheets (the rest of the groups did not hand in photos or handed in photos not usable for this purpose, e.g. because litter was not yet sorted into categories). Based on these pictures, a total of 110 classification mistakes were identified (the most affected categories being crown caps and plastic packaging of sweets and snacks, see [Supplemental material 4](#) for details on which litter items were misclassified). In addition, in 44 cases at least one litter object remained unaccounted for (i.e. it was present on the picture but not recorded in the datasheet). Due to this, approximately 1% of litter items were misclassified or were not accounted for (506 items out of a total of 48,374 litter items classified by groups handing in photos). This value represents a very rough estimate (as photos were not available for all of the registered items or photos often showed overlapping or not clearly distinguishable and recognizable items) and the error is likely higher. Nevertheless, for the purpose of the present study, and due to the large quantity of items classified, we assume this error to be negligible.

2.1.2. Data sources for litter at coastlines

In addition to the river sampling campaign, data from three sampling protocols of coastlines were considered: The ICC, MLW, and the litter monitoring by the OSPAR commission. The ICC is a yearly event organized by the Ocean Conservancy in which volunteers clean up coastlines across the world and classify the collected litter items into 52 categories (Zettler et al., 2017, Ocean Conservancy, 2022). MLW is a project by the European Environment Agency, consisting of an app to collect and classify litter collected by citizen scientists into 164 different categories (EEA, 2022). The OSPAR litter monitoring is regularly conducted at European coastlines along the Atlantic coast, and the encountered litter is classified into 147 categories (OSPAR Commission, 2010, [Supplemental material 2](#)).

For the former two projects, data from the beginning of 2019 to the end of 2021 were considered; while for the OSPAR protocol data from 2019 to 2020 were included in the analysis (no data were yet available for 2021). Only data from countries belonging to the European Union as of the present time were included (therefore excluding the United Kingdom; see details in [Supplemental material 5](#) on data treatment of the three coastline litter protocols).

Overall there was a substantial proportion of sampling events in which no single litter item was registered in the ICC dataset (14% considering data for Europe, 22% considering data for Germany). For the MLW dataset this proportion of sampling events without any litter was low (2%), while in the OSPAR dataset all sampling events had associated litter findings. As it was not possible to assess whether genuinely no litter was found during these samplings or litter data were absent due to other circumstances (e.g. litter being registered as weight data and not individual litter items, or database consolidations without migrating all existent litter categories), sampling events with no litter items from the ICC and MLW datasets were excluded from further analysis. Further, to the best of our knowledge, no data verification protocols for the citizen science coastline samplings (ICC, MLW) were in place that would allow to estimate the error of misplaced items. We assume that the error is similar to the Plastic Pirates riverside sampling (see above). Likewise, for the OSPAR dataset, no estimation of errors can be conducted with the downloaded data, but given that samplings are conducted by trained teams of scientists, it seems safe to assume that also for these data the errors are negligible.

2.1.3. Harmonisation of litter categories across sampling protocols

The dozens of categories of litter items in the sampling protocols for coastlines (ICC, MLW, OSPAR) and the categories of the Plastic Pirates riverside protocol were condensed to 21 categories ([Supplemental material 2](#)). This was done to cover the eleven product groups of the SUPD and further commonly occurring litter items of other materials. All items consisting partially of plastics (e.g. cigarette butts and tetra paks) were considered as plastics in the present study. Likewise, balloons were classified as plastics (even though the majority likely consist of latex, a rubber). This was done because the plastic component has the most detrimental environmental impact (and the impact of fragmented balloon pieces are assumed to be comparable to plastics), and to be in line with the SUPD, addressing these items collectively as SUPs. It was not possible to harmonise data entirely between the four sampling protocols, i.e. litter categories did not always match. For example, the OSPAR protocol lists tetra paks and cigarette butts under the main category of paper items (in this case these items have been reclassified as SUPs). Likewise, the MLW protocol does not differentiate between glass and ceramic shards, and so for the present study it was assumed that all

items registered in this category consisted of glass. In other cases, a category from one sampling protocol (e.g. Plastic Pirates category “crown caps”) is more narrow than the consolidated category (e.g. “metal lids”), resulting in an underestimation of items for the respective sampling and category.

In all protocols, there were categories for fragmented items, items of unknown composition, items of multiple materials, or conglomerates of items associated to a litter source (e.g. “construction materials” from the ICC protocol). Naturally, these items could not be assigned to another category and were considered as other litter or other plastic litter if the material composition was identified by the sampling protocol. Further, data from the coastline sampling protocols were considered as count data even though the sampling protocols list some exceptions, e.g. in the OSPAR protocol, there were some fractional values (which were rounded to the closest integer). Overall, because of the large number of litter items classified with each of the sampling protocols, we consider deviances resulting from this reclassification as minor (see [Supplemental material 2](#) for a detailed list on how each category of each protocol was assigned to the 21 consolidated categories, and [Hapich et al., 2022](#) for a discussion on litter classification issues and the development of a classification system).

2.1.4. Data analysis

For each individual sampling event the proportion of each of the 21 consolidated litter categories was calculated based on the total number of items found during the sampling event. Afterwards, these proportions were averaged across all sampling events, so that the mean of proportions was obtained for each litter category within each sampling protocol. Further, similar to [Cowger et al. \(2022\)](#), bootstrapping was used to establish confidence intervals around the mean of proportions (resampling with replacement with 10,000 repetitions). This was done in R 4.0.2 ([R Core Team 2020](#)) with the RStudio 2022.7.2.576 environment ([RStudio Team, 2022](#)), using the packages `boot` 1.3–28.1 ([Canty and Ripley, 2022](#)), and `car` 3.1–0 ([Fox and Weisberg, 2019](#)).

2.2. Litter reduction scenarios

We developed three different scenarios to estimate the potential reduction of (i) single-use plastics, (ii) overall plastics, and (iii) overall litter items that could result from the implementation of the SUPD. The scenarios revolve around different policy measures introduced by the SUPD to address SUPs as well as fishing gear ([Table 1](#)): Market restrictions (i.e. bans) for plastic cutlery, straws and plates, cotton buds, fast food packaging and cups made from expanded polystyrene, as well as plastic balloon sticks entered into force in July 2021. At the same time, mandatory labelling for plastic cups, tobacco products, and certain sanitary articles was introduced to highlight that the products contain plastic and to inform consumers about adequate disposal.

By July 2024, beverage containers (e.g. plastic bottles and tetra paks) have to be designed in a way that their lids remain attached during use. PET-bottles have to contain at least 25% recycled material by the year 2025, and 30% by 2030. Furthermore, EU Member States need to implement measures to “achieve a measurable quantitative reduction” ([EU Directive 2019/904](#)) regarding the use of take-away food and beverage containers by 2026 compared to 2022. To achieve this, Member States are required to monitor the amount of these items given

Table 2

Different scenarios for the reduction of litter items addressed by the Single-Use Plastics Directive. The baseline are litter quantities reported by four different protocols of the years 2019 to 2021 (see main text for details). Percentages indicate the estimated amount of reduction of litter items for the respective scenario. “Best case” scenario = widespread reduction of all types of plastics addressed by the Directive. “Moderate improvements” scenario = complete reduction of banned plastics and partial reduction of other addressed plastics. “Only bans” scenario = complete reduction of banned items and no reductions of other types of plastics addressed by the Directive. See the main text for details regarding the reasoning behind these assumptions.

% reduction of litter quantities (2019 to 2021)	“Best case” scenario	“Moderate improvements” scenario	“Only bans” scenario
Plastic bags	100%	25%	0%
Plastic bottles	100%	50%	0%
Plastic lids	100%	50%	0%
Takeaway and fast food packaging (incl. disposable coffee cups and lids) ^[1]	100%	50%	25%
Plastic cutlery and plastic plates (incl. plastic coffee stirrers and plastic straws)	100%	100%	100%
Plastic packaging for sweets, crisps, etc.	100%	25%	0%
Cotton buds with plastic rod	100%	100%	100%
Wet wipes, tampons, and sanitary towels	100%	25%	0%
Cigarette butts	100%	25%	0%
Balloons ^[2]	100%	25%	0%
Plastic fishing gear	100%	50%	0%

^[1]These items are grouped in the present study, a subset of these items (those made of expanded polystyrene) are banned by the Directive. Therefore we assumed an overall reduction of roughly 25% of items in this category for the “only bans” scenario ([Supplemental material 6](#)).

^[2]Balloon plastic sticks are also addressed by the Directive but omitted here as no data about them were collected by the analysed protocols.

out to consumers but are free to choose adequate measures to reduce their consumption (e.g. requiring suppliers to offer reusable alternatives, or taxing single-use containers). Through extended producer responsibility schemes for a range of SUPs, producers are required to cover the costs of cleaning up litter as well as for collection, transport and waste treatment, and for consumer awareness campaigns by the end of 2024 (for cigarette filters and plastic packaging already in the beginning of 2023). Finally, awareness raising measures have to be introduced to inform consumers about negative impacts of littering, correct disposal of products, and alternative options to using SUPs ([Table 1](#)).

Scenarios were created by making different assumptions regarding the effectiveness of these measures in reducing litter occurrence for eleven categories of items: The first scenario, “best case”, assumed that all items addressed by the SUPD disappear completely as litter in the environment (i.e. items addressed by bans and by the other above-mentioned measures; [Table 2](#)). The second scenario, “moderate improvements” made three assumptions: (i) items affected by bans disappear completely as litter in the environment; (ii) items addressed by design requirements (i.e. plastic beverage containers and their lids),

consumption reduction targets (plastic take-away and fast food containers as well as plastic cups), and collection targets (plastic bottles and plastic fishing gear) are reduced by 50%; and (iii) items addressed by other measures such as extended producer responsibility, requiring producers to contribute to education campaigns and cleanups or introducing labelling, are reduced by 25% (Table 2). Assumptions (ii) and (iii) are based on the following considerations: The design requirement is obligatory for all producers and therefore has the potential to reduce the pollution by the addressed products thoroughly (although exemptions for some beverage containers may be implemented). Regarding the consumption reduction and collection targets, the EU obliges Member States to implement adequate reduction measures (e.g. deposit-refund schemes), to submit a description of measures to the EU Commission and to monitor the amount of take-away food and beverage containers placed on the market to evaluate the progress. Through these mechanisms, a tangible litter reduction for these items can be expected. Extended producer responsibility schemes and further measures for certain SUP items have to be established, but, in contrast, the design of those measures is left to the EU Member States. They may subsequently implement differing schemes, some of which are likely more, and others less ambitious and successful in reducing litter. Finally, the third scenario, “only bans”, assumed that the ban leads to the complete disappearance of addressed litter items, yet all further measures are ineffective (Table 2).

For the purpose of simplification, other factors that could have a minor influence on these scenarios were ignored (e.g. that plastic straws will still be required by people with certain disabilities, Larrington-Spencer et al., 2021). Further, the scenarios do not predict the development of litter quantities in the future but estimate the potential of all measures of the SUPD to reduce litter in the environment based on quantities found in 2019 to 2021. Items for which market restrictions came into effect in the second half of 2021 were additionally analysed separately, to allow for a preliminary evaluation of this measure.

3. Results

3.1. Litter at riversides and coastlines in Germany and the European Union

Substantial amounts of litter items have been collected by employing the different sampling protocols in the years 2019 to 2021 (at least close to 10,000 items in the OSPAR dataset for Germany and more than 1 million items in the ICC dataset considering coastlines in Europe, Table 3). The mean proportions of items revealed that cigarette butts, glass shards and snack packaging were among the most frequently found items at riversides in Germany (Table 3, Fig. 1, the entire dataset is available as Supplemental material 7 and at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7064093>). At coastlines in Germany, the ICC protocol reported lots of cigarette butts, snack packaging and not further defined SUPs and other plastics, while in the OSPAR protocol SUPs were not prominent and mainly fishing gear and other plastic objects were found (Table 3, Fig. 1). Similarly, considering mean proportions for coastlines in Europe, the OSPAR protocol reported mainly other plastic objects and fishing gear, while cigarette butts were among the most frequently found

items in the citizen science protocols (ICC and MLW), although they also reported large proportions of other plastic litter. Overall, the proportion of SUPs were comparatively low in the OSPAR dataset while they made up more than 40% in the citizen science protocols at riversides and coastlines alike. The overall proportion of plastic litter (including SUPs) was lowest at riversides investigated by the Plastic Pirates protocol (54%) and substantially higher in all other sampling protocols, including OSPAR (more than 80%; Table 3, Fig. 1).

3.2. Estimated litter reduction for different scenarios

In the “best case” scenario, SUPs at riversides in Germany would disappear entirely (as only such SUPs addressed by the SUPD were categorized in the Plastic Pirates sampling), and their reduction at coastlines in Germany and the European Union would amount to 75% or more of all SUPs, depending on the sampling and environment in question. For plastics in general, the reduction for the different litter samplings would range from 46 to 81%, while overall litter items would be reduced by 42–58% (Fig. 2A). For the scenario “moderate improvements”, SUPs found in the samplings would be reduced by 27–41%. Overall plastic items encountered would be reduced by 21–30%, while expected reductions for total litter are in the range of 13–25% (Fig. 2B). For the scenario “only bans”, reductions of SUPs amount to 4–11% considering the citizen science samplings and are slightly higher for the OSPAR samplings (14 and 17%, respectively). The reduction of total plastics as well as total litter items in the “only bans” scenario would amount to about 2–3% for riversides in Germany, to 2–6% for coastlines in Germany and 4–7% considering coastlines in the EU (Fig. 2C).

In order to compare which measures of the SUPD could potentially be most effective in reducing litter quantities in the environment for the individual products, a closer look at the “moderate improvements” scenario was taken (as the scenarios “best case” and “only bans” assumed full effectiveness and no effectiveness for all measures, respectively, therefore not allowing for comparison): The largest effect could be seen for the OSPAR sampling for measures addressing fishing gear (a reduction of 11 and 21% for coastlines in Europe and Germany, respectively). For the citizen science samplings (Plastic Pirates, ICC, MLW) measures addressing cigarette butts showed a reduction of about 5%. For all other measures overall litter reductions in all sampling protocols were less than 5% (Table 4).

It was further assessed which proportion of overall litter is covered by policy measures. Depending on the sampling, the proportion of litter covered varies between 42 and 58% (Supplemental material 8). Bans apply to 2–6% of litter items. Design requirements, consumption reduction, and collection targets apply to 5–45% of items (the higher proportions correspond to the OSPAR protocol), while “soft” measures apply to 6–37% (the higher proportions correspond to the citizen science protocols in this case; Supplemental material 8).

To evaluate whether the bans of the SUPD had an immediate effect, the mean proportions of addressed items (i.e. cotton buds, plastic cutlery and plates) were analysed separately before and after enactment of this measure. Results showed that the proportion of these items varied very little before and after enactment (less than 2%; Supplemental material 9).

Table 3

Mean proportions (with bootstrapped 2.5 and 97.5% confidence intervals, respectively) of litter items found at riversides and coastlines in Germany and European countries (including Germany) for which data were available according to different sampling protocols (n = number of individual sampling events analysed). The total count of litter items found for the respective category is mentioned in square brackets (these values do not add up to the proportional values as the mean proportions were used – see main text of manuscript for details). Marine Litter Watch did not report data for Germany in the respective time period (2019 to 2021) and OSPAR did not report data for the year 2021. Mean proportions of 5% or higher are highlighted in bold. The last column shows whether a litter category was considered for the analysis within the three proposed scenarios (see Table 2 for assumptions of the scenarios).

Litter items	Plastic Pirates (Riversides in Germany, 2019 – 2021), n = 379	International Coastal Cleanup (Coastlines in Germany, 2019 – 2021), n = 227	OSPAR (Coastlines in Germany, 2019 – 2020), n = 59	International Coastal Cleanup (Coastlines in 25 European countries, 2019 – 2021), n = 3,181	Marine Litter Watch (Coastlines in 14 European countries, 2019 – 2021), n = 412	OSPAR (coastlines in 8 European countries, 2019 – 2020), n = 665	Scenario
Plastic bags (SUP)	5.4 (4.6–6.6)% [2,281]	6.2 (4.3–8.9)% [3,908]	2.2 (1.4–3.9)% [123]	4.2 (3.9–4.6)% [40,852]	6.6 (5.7–7.9)% [48,881]	2.2 (1.9–2.7)% [6,518]	Best, Moderate
Plastic bottles for beverages (SUP)	1.4 (1.1–1.8)% [556]	2.9 (1.7–5.0)% [655]	0.5 (0.3–0.7)% [38]	4.9 (4.5–5.3)% [40,090]	3.0 (2.5–3.7)% [10,744]	1.5 (1.3–1.8)% [5,697]	Best, Moderate
Plastic lids of beverage bottles (SUP)	1.9 (1.6–2.3)% [936]	1.6 (1.2–2.2)% [2,019]	1.9 (1.4–2.6)% [176]	3.5 (3.3–3.8)% [52,638]	4.5 (4.0–5.1)% [21,715]	3.5 (3.3–3.8)% [36,512]	Best, Moderate
Takeaway and fast food packaging (incl. disposable coffee cups and lids), made from expanded polystyrene and other plastics	2.0 (1.7–2.5)% [1,138]	6.4 (4.7–8.7)% [1,199]	1.3 (0.9–1.8)% [141]	4.6 (4.2–4.9)% [14,050]	3.0 (2.7–3.5)% [16,202]	1.6 (1.4–1.9)% [7,918]	Best, Moderate, Only bans
Plastic cutlery and plastic plates (incl. plastic coffee stirrers and plastic straws; SUP)	1.1 (0.9–1.4)% [579]	3.7 (2.5–5.8)% [2,498]	0.5 (0.3–0.8)% [42]	3.8 (3.5–4.1)% [79,429]	2.7 (2.3–3.1)% [14,811]	0.6 (0.5–0.6)% [3,696]	Best, Moderate, Only bans
Plastic packaging for sweets, crisps, etc. (SUP)	10.7 (9.7–12.1)% [5,572]	11.3 (9.0–14.4)% [10,222]	1.7 (1.2–2.7)% [147]	6.4 (6.0–6.8)% [52,947]	5.6 (5.0–6.3)% [31,469]	2.6 (2.3–2.8)% [11,279]	Best, Moderate
Cotton buds with plastic rod ('Q-tips'; SUP)	0.1 (<0.1–0.2)% [44]	na	0.9 (0.4–1.9)% [100]	na	2.7 (2.2–3.4)% [14,252]	2.7 (2.3–3.1)% [24,366]	Best, Moderate, Only bans
Wet wipes, tampons, and sanitary towels (SUP)	1.9 (1.5–2.4)% [1,142]	<0.1 (<0.1–<0.1)% [194]	0% [0]	0.1 (0.1–0.2)% [4,272]	0.7 (0.5–1.4)% [2,465]	0.3 (0.2–0.4)% [1,269]	Best, Moderate
Cigarette butts (SUP)	18.9 (17.0–20.9)% [18,235]	18.3 (14.9–22.1)% [53,685]	0.8 (0.4–1.7)% [60]	19.9 (19.0–20.8)% [616,116]	20.5 (18.3–23.1)% [180,763]	3.6 (2.9–4.6)% [12,257]	Best, Moderate
Balloons (SUP)	0.3 (0.2–0.5) [147]	0.8 (0.3–3.0)% [310]	1.1 (0.6–2.4)% [100]	0.7 (0.6–1.0)% [6,328]	0.4 (0.3–0.5)% [748]	0.4 (0.3–0.5)% [4,089]	Best, Moderate
Single-use plastics, other (SUP)	na	17.0 (13.5–21.2)% [7,302]	1.0 (0.7–1.3)% [128]	6.6 (6.1–7.1)% [50,654]	4.5 (3.9–5.3)% [11,103]	2.5 (2.2–2.9)% [11,190]	
Plastic fishing gear	na	na	41.5 (35.5–47.8) [4,101]	na	8.2 (7.1–9.5)% [28,889]	22.8 (21.4–24.4)% [328,424]	
Other plastic objects	10.2 (9.0–11.7)% [6,638]	14.9 (12.1–18.2)% [13,520]	32.1 (27.2–37.0)% [3,433]	30.7 (29.4–31.9)% [365,733]	23.4 (21.6–25.3)% [133,602]	46.2 (44.6–48.0)% [376,877]	
Metal beverage cans	1.9 (1.3–3.2)% [730]	2.3 (1.3–4.5)% [675]	0.1 (0.1–0.4)% [7]	3.7 (3.4–4.1)% [28,074]	1.5 (1.2–2.0)% [7,530]	0.3 (0.2–0.4)% [540]	
Metal bottle caps	6.4 (5.5–7.4)% [11,080]	3.4 (2.2–5.5)% [1,606]	0.1 (<0.1–0.2)% [9]	1.5 (1.3–1.7)% [13,073]	0.8 (0.7–1.0)% [4,914]	0.2 (0.2–0.3)% [787]	
Other metal objects	4.5 (4.0–5.2)% [2,806]	na	1.1 (0.6–1.8)% [119]	na	1.6 (1.4–2.0)% [9,502]	0.8 (0.7–0.9)% [2,429]	
Glass bottles for drinks	3.2 (2.8–3.8)% [1,549]	3.0 (2.0–4.6)% [3,031]	0.8 (0.4–1.9)% [82]	2.4 (2.2–2.7)% [29,142]	3.4 (2.7–4.4)% [14,644] ⁽¹⁾	1.0 (0.8–1.4)% [3,023]	
Glass pieces	11.9 (10.4–13.6)% [11,175]	0.3 (0.1–0.9)% [1,391]	Na	1.2 (1.0–1.4)% [29,936]	na	na	
Other glass objects	0.4 (0.2–0.6)% [131]	na	0.8 (0.4–2.2)% [31]	na	1.3 (0.9–2.2)% [4,834]	0.8 (0.6–1.1)% [2,165]	

(continued on next page)

Table 3 (continued)

Litter items	Plastic Pirates (Riversides in Germany, 2019 – 2021), n = 379	International Coastal Cleanup (Coastlines in Germany, 2019 – 2021), n = 227	OSPAR (Coastlines in Germany, 2019 – 2020), n = 59	International Coastal Cleanup (Coastlines in 25 European countries, 2019 – 2021), n = 3,181	Marine Litter Watch (Coastlines in 14 European countries, 2019 – 2021), n = 412	OSPAR (coastlines in 8 European countries, 2019 – 2020), n = 665	Scenario
Paper	9.7 (8.6–11.1)% [6,306]	0.1 (<0.1–0.9)% [1,479]	0.6 (0.3–1.0)% [51]	0.3 (0.3–0.3)% [6,672]	1.2 (1.0–1.5)% [7,340]	1.0 (0.8–1.4)% [3,436]	
Other waste, undefined or other material	8.1 (7.1–9.2)% [5,459]	7.9 (6.0–10.5)% [2,168]	11.1 (7.9–16.9)% [1,085]	5.4 (5.0–5.9)% [25,708]	4.3 (3.8–5.1)% [14,445]	5.4 (4.9–6.2)% [13,524]	
Total single-use plastics	43.7 (41.7–45.8) [30,630]	68.2 (64.1–71.9)% [82,123]	11.8 (10.0–13.8)% [1,055]	54.8 (53.6–56.0)% [976,824]	54.2 (51.9–56.6)% [353,153]	21.4 (20.2–22.8)% [124,791]	
Total plastics (including single-use plastics)	53.9 (51.9–56.0)% [37,268]	83.0 (79.7–85.8)% [95,643]	85.4 (79.8–88.7)% [8,589]	85.5 (84.8–86.1) [1,342,557]	85.8 (84.3–87.2)% [515,644]	90.5 (89.4–91.4)% [830,092]	
Total litter items	100% [76,504]	100% [105,993]	100% [9,973]	100% [1,455,714]	100% [578,853]	100% [855,996]	

⁽¹⁾Glass bottles and glass pieces are reported within one category in the MLW protocol.

Fig. 1. Composition of litter found at riversides (PP = Plastic Pirates sampling) and coastlines (ICC = International Coastal Cleanup, MLW = Marine Litter Watch, OSPAR = sampling protocol by the OSPAR Commission) in Germany and the European Union, respectively. The values represent the mean of proportions of litter items of each category (see main text for details).

4. Discussion

4.1. Reliability of data and developed scenarios

Most of the data used in the present analysis came from citizen science projects. While the data quality of studies involving volunteers not formally educated in sciences is at times questioned, it has been shown that these data do not lack behind data collected by “professional scientists”, if adequate data quality control mechanisms are in place (Hidalgo-Ruz and Thiel, 2015, Zettler et al., 2017). For the Plastic Pirates these consisted, for example, of photos available for data corroboration (see details in section 2.1.1. above) and detailing under which conditions datasets were included or excluded. Moreover, the protocol of the Plastic Pirates is based on concise research questions and methods adequate for the use in schools (Dittmann et al., 2022). It has to be emphasized that the current study would not have been possible without relying on citizen science data, i.e. no other data for litter items existed across these extensive temporal and geographical scales for the investigated environments.

Regarding the suitability of data for the presented scenarios, the citizen science datasets are naturally collected at spots that are easily accessible and are therefore likely to coincide with spots that are frequently visited by many people, and where cleanups take place more regularly. This is reflected in the items found, especially when comparing data for coastlines from the citizen science protocols (ICC and MLW) to the OSPAR protocol. The latter is reporting much more fishery debris and, for some datasets, large quantities of unidentifiable, potentially fragmented plastic objects. It is likely that at least some of these fragmented items originate from regulated items, therefore the scenarios slightly underestimate the effectiveness of measures of the SUPD in this regard. Uncertainties also arise from the harmonisation of litter item categories across four different sampling protocols (see details in section 2.1.3. above), and the fact that only count data were considered (weight and/or volume data were not available from the data sources).

The estimated effectiveness of certain instruments of the SUPD is also subject to uncertainties, e.g. bans might not be 100% effective as has been shown for market restrictions imposed on plastic bags (Nielsen

Fig. 2. Different scenarios for the reduction of single-use plastics, total plastics, and total litter according to the samplings analysed and based on mean proportions of litter findings (Plastic Pirates investigated riversides, other samplings investigated coastlines). (A) Estimated reduction of the “best case” scenario if bans and further measures of the SUPD are 100% effective, i.e. widespread reduction of all types of items addressed by the Directive. (B) Estimated reduction if bans of the Directive are 100% effective and other measures lead to moderate improvements (see main text for details), i.e. complete reduction of banned items and partial reduction of other addressed products. (C) Estimated reductions if only bans are 100% effective at reducing litter in the environment and further measures are ineffective, i.e. complete reduction of banned items and no reductions of other types of products addressed by the Directive. For details of the assumptions see [Table 2](#).

Table 4

Reductions of individual products, based on mean proportions of litter registered by the four different protocols and found by the “moderate improvements” scenario. Values at 5% and higher are highlighted in bold. For assumptions regarding the effectiveness of measures of [EU Directive 2019/904](#) see [Table 2](#).

Measure(s) on	Riversides in Germany (Plastic Pirates)	Coastlines in Germany (International Coastal Cleanup)	Coastlines in Germany (OSPAR)	Coastlines in EU27 (International Coastal Cleanup)	Coastlines in EU27 (Marine Litter Watch)	Coastlines in EU27 (OSPAR)
Plastic bags	1.4%	1.5%	0.6%	1.1%	1.6%	0.5%
Plastic bottles	0.7%	1.4%	0.2%	2.4%	1.5%	0.7%
Plastic lids	0.9%	0.8%	0.9%	1.8%	2.3%	1.8%
Takeaway and fast food packaging (incl. disposable coffee cups and lids)	1.0%	3.2%	0.6%	2.3%	1.5%	0.8%
Plastic cutlery and plastic plates (incl. plastic coffee stirrers and plastic straws)	1.1%	3.7%	0.5%	3.8%	2.7%	0.6%
Plastic packaging for sweets, crisps, etc.	2.7%	2.8%	0.4%	1.6%	1.4%	0.6%
Cotton buds with plastic rod	0.1%	na	0.9%	na	2.7%	2.7%
Wet wipes, tampons, and sanitary towels	0.5%	<0.1%	0%	<0.1%	0.2%	0.1%
Cigarette butts	4.7%	4.6%	0.2%	5.0%	5.1%	0.9%
Balloons	0.1%	0.2%	0.3%	0.2%	0.1%	0.1%
Plastic fishing gear	na	na	20.7%	na	4.1%	11.4%

et al., 2019) and banned items may also reach European countries by sea. Assumptions regarding the effectiveness of other measures in our scenarios to reduce litter quantities in the environment, such as extended producer responsibility and awareness raising, are only insufficiently supported by other studies (but see Harris et al., 2021). Further, some items banned under the SUPD were not included in the current analysis (i.e. plastic sticks for balloons).

4.2. Comparing litter at riversides and coastlines in Germany and the European Union

Plastic items were ubiquitous pollutants in all of the considered samplings, their occurrence ranging from 54 to 91% of overall litter. Many of these objects consisted of SUPs, although this proportion varied largely between the samplings: Citizen science protocols reported between 44 and 68% of SUPs, while the proportion was much lower for OSPAR samplings (12% for Germany, 21% for the EU). In contrast, OSPAR samplings reported much more fishing litter and more other plastic litter. Schöneich-Argent et al. (2019) also found large proportions of fishing gear at OSPAR sampling sites on German islands of the North Sea but not necessarily so at other sampling sites on the same island. High proportions of fishing gear compared to river samplings have also been reported from other coastal regions of the world (Schneider et al., 2021). The OSPAR protocol requires sampling sites to be exposed to the open sea, and to be free of buildings, which could explain the difference in litter composition (OSPAR Commission, 2010, Schöneich-Argent et al., 2019).

Comparing citizen science data from German riversides and coastlines, the proportion of items such as glass shards, paper, and metal bottle caps was higher in riverside samplings. A similar result was observed in Chile by Rech et al. (2014), who also found more non-buoyant (e.g. metal and glass) and short-term buoyant items (e.g. paper and cigarette butts) at riversides compared to coastlines. An explanation could be that input of positively buoyant plastics from sea-based sources contributed to lowering the proportion of other litter items, or that buoyant items at riversides get transported into the river and washed away.

Cigarette butts were the most frequently found individual item in all citizen science datasets (with very similar proportions of about 20%). This is not surprising as cigarette butts are one of the most littered items worldwide (an estimated 4.5 trillion cigarette butts are littered annually, Araújo and Costa, 2019). Other SUPs such as food containers, plastic bottle caps, and plastic wrapping for food products were also shown to be among the most frequently occurring items in large-scale studies (e.g. Nelms et al., 2017, Morales-Caselles et al., 2021, Baxter et al., 2022), although the exact composition might be specific for the region investigated. This is exemplified by a study investigating beaches of seven countries in the Mediterranean Sea, where cotton buds accounted for a large share of identifiable litter (Vlachogianni et al., 2018), while these were almost absent in samplings of the present study in Germany, suggesting differences in the use and disposal of products.

A comparison of data for items addressed by bans before and after the introduction of the SUPD showed no clear result. This was expected, as firstly, it is unlikely that litter in the environment disappears within half a year after the introduction of a ban, and secondly, it is still legal to distribute remaining stocks of these items. Hence, the items do not disappear from the market immediately and are likely to be found as litter in the environment during this transitional phase (also see Clayton et al., 2021 describing the phasing out of SUPs in countries in the Caribbean).

Overall, many of the items encountered in the samplings are usually not cleaned up due to their small size or because they are being located at sites where no regular cleanups take place (Altvater et al., 2022). Further, transport processes of litter from one environmental compartment to another, e.g. from the riparian environment towards the sea (e.g. Hoellein and Rochman, 2021, van Emmerik et al., 2022) as well as

from the open sea towards the coastline (e.g. van Sebille et al., 2020, Morales-Caselles et al., 2021), are complex and usually non-linear. In addition, plastic litter is often being transformed during passage (e.g. it degrades and is colonised by organisms; Hoellein and Rochman, 2021), causing harm on multiple ecological levels (Bucci et al., 2020). This emphasizes the need for preventive measures to reduce the input of plastic litter into the environment.

4.3. Potential of the EU Single-use plastics Directive to reduce plastic pollution

The “best case” scenario assumed that all litter items addressed by any measure of the SUPD would be absent from the environment in the future. The results of this hypothetical scenario show that litter quantities in riparian and coastal environments could be reduced substantially if measures were 100% effective in avoiding littering of the addressed SUP items (upwards of 40% for overall litter and by 46% to 81% for plastic litter, depending on the different protocols that were considered). Although we are aware that the assumption of a 100% reduction of addressed SUP litter items is highly unrealistic, this scenario demonstrates that the SUPD offers important levers to reduce environmental (plastic) pollution. In other words, the SUPD has the potential to significantly cut litter amounts in the environment, which is also reflected by the proportion of litter items the SUPD covers with policy measures (42–58%, depending on the sampling protocol). However, our analysis likewise illustrated that measures for several addressed groups of SUP items require stronger regulations.

The “only bans” scenario reveals that with the bans already in place, only a marginal reduction of overall litter and plastic litter quantities can be achieved (between 4 and 7% at coastlines in Europe and only 2 to 6% for sampling sites in Germany). These values are in line with a study by Herberz et al. (2020), estimating a reduction of marine pollution by 5.5% in the EU as a result of the SUP product bans embedded in the SUPD. Similarly, a study conducted to underpin the impact assessment carried out by the European Commission for the proposal of the SUPD assumed marginal reductions of most litter items related to overall litter quantities in the marine environment (European Commission, 2018b). The results of this scenario highlight that in order to significantly reduce litter volumes and the associated environmental impact, it is crucial that the other measures foreseen in the SUPD take effect. Extended producer responsibility schemes, measures for consumption reduction, product design requirements, and information campaigns hence need to be well-implemented as well as ambitious, and they should set high targets for litter reduction. If these measures were successful in halving or reducing littering of certain items by a quarter, litter quantities could still be reduced significantly, as is illustrated by the “moderate improvements” scenario (reductions would range from 13% to 25% considering overall litter and from 22 to 30% for plastic litter).

With regard to the implementation of policy measures beyond the product bans, it is important to note that some of these instruments are clearly defined (such as product design requirements) or have a predictable outcome: The 90% collection target for beverage plastic bottles will lead to the introduction of deposit-refund systems in several Member States which have been reluctant to introduce such a system in the past (deposit-refund systems have a proven track record to successfully keep items out of the environment; Zhou et al., 2020, Calabrese et al., 2021). The mode of implementation for other measures, including the introduction of extended producer responsibility schemes, is left to the individual EU Member States and the success of the measure therefore uncertain. For instance, the SUPD does not define what the term “cleanup” encompasses (e.g. cleaning intervals, geographical scope; Altvater et al., 2022), and Member States might thus decide to solely focus on economically important tourist beaches in their cleanup activities. This makes it difficult to predict the level of ambition of the measures in each Member State as well as the effectiveness of those measures. A look at the existing literature does not necessarily offer

Fig. 3. (A) Measures of the Single-Use Plastics Directive allocated on the waste hierarchy. The waste hierarchy illustrates the priority in the treatment of products, from the best use (at the top) towards the worst use (towards the bottom). Modified from [Penca \(2018\)](#). (B) No solution to the single-use problem: single-use cutlery and cups made from paper, bamboo and “bioplastic”, wrapped in conventional plastic packaging in a supermarket in Germany. Photo by Tim Kiessling (Creative Commons license CC BY 4.0).

reason for optimism: in one of the rare studies evaluating the potential of policy measures in reducing the actual litter quantities present in the environment, [Harris et al. \(2021\)](#) found that litter at the coastline was not reduced following the introduction of extended producer responsibility in Canada, despite a higher material collection and recovery rate. Similarly, [Baxter et al. \(2022\)](#) found that Canadian legislation with measures comparable to the ones in the SUPD (e.g. bans and extended

producer responsibility) falls short to adequately reduce the SUP pollution problem.

Based on the data presented in this study, it becomes clear that to effectively reduce environmental litter quantities, other measures are necessary, actually reducing the use of SUPs and other single-use items. Furthermore, the scenario analysis provides some insights regarding individual litter items. First, cigarette butts are the most frequently

found litter item across the citizen science sampling protocols. Measures to reduce cigarette butt litter hence have the potential to considerably reduce overall litter quantities (measured per count) found at riversides and coastlines. This is the case even if these measures reduce litter occurrence of the respective items to a smaller share (e.g. 25 as assumed in the “moderate improvements” scenario, compared to an assumed effectiveness of 100% for bans). Yet, under the current SUPD provisions, only rather “soft” policy measures apply to cigarette filters (such as information campaigns and labelling). Second, wrappers and food packaging are abundantly found, both at coastlines and riversides. Often this litter results from small, individually wrapped sweets and snacks. Similar to cigarette filters, they often present tiny litter items and their removal from the environment can be difficult and costly (Castaldi et al., 2021, Altvater et al., 2022, Conradi and Sánchez-Moyano, 2022). A more sustainable solution to reduce this type of litter would be a reorientation towards reusable and durable packaging solutions, as well as an overall reduction of packaging. Member States responsible for implementation and EU-bodies responsible for monitoring should therefore make sure that incentives are set for reusable packaging options and packaging reduction.

4.4. Recommendations for and beyond the Single-Use plastics Directive

The present analysis has highlighted that, in addition to product bans, the other measures foreseen in the SUPD need to be effective to ensure that the SUPD brings about a significant change in terms of litter quantities at shorelines and riversides (Table 4). As the implementation of measures of the SUPD will only take full effect in the coming years and is partially subject to the country-specific implementation by EU Member States, a complimentary monitoring of addressed litter items is necessary to evaluate the effectiveness of this novel legislation in reducing environmental plastic pollution in the coming years. Data originating from citizen science projects have been invaluable to conduct the present study. Similarly, at this time, only citizen science data cover the necessary spatio-temporal scale to allow for this kind of monitoring and evaluation, and these data could also be useful for a cost-benefit-analysis of the SUPD.

While existing legislation has often been focusing on end-of-life measures (e.g. waste collection and recycling), the SUPD includes several novel measures that target the environmental litter problem towards the top of the waste hierarchy (see Fig. 3A). Apart from the SUP product bans, these include, for instance, the design requirements for plastic beverage containers. The design requirement for tethered caps is a first step in the right direction, but in our view similar design requirements need to be adopted for other products (such as beverage containers made from metal or glass), and should further address other aspects of SUP packaging (such as fitting packaging sizes to the packaged products, or setting standards to establish refillable products; see Gustavo et al., 2018).

A shortcoming of the SUPD is that it entails only few concrete provisions for a transition from single-use to reusable, long-lasting products and packaging. This poses the risk that banned SUP items are substituted by single-use items made from other materials (Fig. 3B). In fact, existing literature shows that consumers often choose single-use alternatives instead of reusable ones when faced with a single-use alternative to plastic bags (such as thinner, unregulated plastic bags or paper bags; Schnurr et al., 2018, Taylor, 2019, Adeyanju et al., 2021). This offsets the effect of the initial measure and shifts environmental impacts to other compartments, e.g. the alternative may contribute more to global warming than the replaced article (Civancik-Uslu et al., 2019, Hoge and Brandão, 2020). Moreover, this approach does not only offer little incentive to consumers to change their consumption and littering behaviour, it also does not encourage manufacturers to change their business models. Therefore, the EU should align its policies more effectively with the waste hierarchy (which it has imposed on itself as a fundamental principle) and truly prioritise waste reduction and re-use

options (Fig. 3A).

In conclusion, shifting away from the modus operandi of the global throw-away society with an excessive consumption of single-use and short-lived products (regardless of material), requires further bold legislative guidance towards business models catering to a society caring about truly sustainable (i.e. reusable, valuable, and durable) products and packaging. Recent studies on consumer behaviour indicate that citizens are prepared for bold solutions (Khedr et al., 2023). Only these can contribute to curb the global production of plastics and the associated dire environmental consequences of future emissions of plastics, which are projected to increase dramatically even given current global ambitious legislative action (Borrelle et al., 2020).

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

All data used is publicly available. The data from the Plastic Pirates project is available at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7064093>

Acknowledgements

The present study could not have been realized without the enthusiastic support of schoolchildren, teachers, and volunteers collecting litter data at riversides in Germany – their collaboration is greatly appreciated (see [Supplemental material 1](#))! Likewise, we appreciate all the effort from contributors to the International Coastal Cleanup, the Marine Litter Watch, and the OSPAR datasets. In this regard, we also wish to thank the Ocean Conservancy, the European Environmental Agency and the OSPAR Commission for making their litter data publicly available. Many people throughout the years contributed to the Plastic Pirates project, we are grateful to colleagues from Kiel Science Factory, the Ecologic Institute, the German Aerospace Centre, and familie redlich! Discussions with Mateja Grego (National Institute of Biology, Slovenia), Meritxell Abril Cuevas (University of Vic, Spain) and Carla Lourenço (Ciência Viva, Portugal) were important for the assessment of single-use plastics at riversides. We are grateful for the comments by three anonymous reviewers which have helped to substantially improve this manuscript. Funding for the present study came from the Federal Ministry of Education and Research in Germany (BMBF). MT was supported by the European Union’s H2020 research and innovation programme MINKE project (under Grant Agreement No 101008724).

Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.wasman.2023.03.042>.

References

- Adam, I., Walker, T.R., Bezerra, J.C., Clayton, A., 2020. Policies to reduce single-use plastic marine pollution in West Africa. *Mar. Policy* 116, 103928.
- Addamo, A. M., Laroche, P., Hanke, G., 2017. Top marine beach litter items in Europe. A review and synthesis based on beach litter data. MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter. Report No. EUR29249, 148335.
- Adeyanju, G.C., Augustine, T.M., Volkmann, S., Oyebamiji, U.A., Ran, S., Osobajo, O.A., Oitoju, A., 2021. Effectiveness of intervention on behaviour change against use of non-biodegradable plastic bags: a systematic review. *Discover Sustainability* 2, 13.
- Altvater, S., Sina, S., Hirschnitz-Garbers, M., Meinecke, L., Hinzmann, M., Gerstetter, C., 2022. EU Single-Use Plastics Directive – analysis of provisions and potential measures regarding extended producer responsibility. Final report, Texte 42/2022, German Environment Agency.
- Araújo, M.C.B., Costa, M.F., 2019. A critical review of the issue of cigarette butt pollution in coastal environments. *Environ. Res.* 172, 137–149.

- Aretoulaki, E., Ponis, S., Plakas, G., Agalinos, K., 2021. Marine plastic littering: a review of socio economic impacts. *J. Sustainability Sci. Manage.* 16, 276–300.
- Bassi, S.A., Boldrin, A., Faraca, G., Astrup, T.F., 2020. Extended producer responsibility: How to unlock the environmental and economic potential of plastic packaging waste? *Resources Conserv. Recycl.* 162, 105030.
- Baxter, L., Lucas, Z., Walker, T.R., 2022. Evaluating Canada's single-use plastic mitigation policies via brand audit and beach cleanup data to reduce plastic pollution. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 176, 113460.
- Beaumont, N.J., Aanesen, M., Austen, M.C., Börger, T., Clark, J.R., Cole, M., Hooper, T., Lindeque, P., Pascoe, C., Wyles, K.J., 2019. Global ecological, social and economic impacts of marine plastic. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 142, 189–195.
- Blettler, M., Ulla, M.A., Rabuffetti, A.P., Garello, N., 2017. Plastic pollution in freshwater ecosystems: macro-, meso-, and microplastic debris in a floodplain lake. *Environ. Monit. Assess.* 189, 1–13.
- Borg, K., Lennox, A., Kaufman, S., Tull, F., Prime, R., Rogers, L., Dunstan, E., 2022. Curbing plastic consumption: a review of single-use plastic behaviour change interventions. *J. Clean. Prod.* 344, 131077.
- Borrelle, S.B., Ringma, J., Law, K.L., Monnahan, C.C., Lebreton, L., McGivern, A., Murphy, E., Jambeck, J., Leonard, G.H., Hilleary, M.A., Eriksen, M., Possingham, H. P., de Frond, H., Gerber, L.R., Polidoro, B., Tahir, A., Bernard, M., Mallos, N., Barnes, M., Rochman, C.M., 2020. Predicted growth in plastic waste exceeds efforts to mitigate plastic pollution. *Science* 369, 1515–1518.
- Brahney, J., Hallerud, M., Heim, E., Hahnenberger, M., Sukumaran, S., 2020. Plastic rain in protected areas of the United States. *Science* 368, 1257–1260.
- Bucci, K., Tulio, M., Rochman, C.M., 2020. What is known and unknown about the effects of plastic pollution: a meta-analysis and systematic review. *Ecol. Appl.* 30, e02044.
- Calabrese, A., Costa, R., Levialdi Ghiron, N., Menichini, T., Miscoli, V., Tiburzi, L., 2021. Operating modes and cost burdens for the European deposit-refund systems: a systematic approach for their analysis and design. *J. Clean. Prod.* 288, 125600.
- Canadian Government, 2021. Government of Canada moving forward with banning harmful single-use plastics. Environment and Climate Change Canada. Available from: <<https://www.canada.ca/en/environment-climate-change/news/2021/12/government-of-canada-moving-forward-with-banning-harmful-single-use-plastics.html>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- Canadian Government, 2021. Order Adding a Toxic Substance to Schedule 1 to the Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999: SOR/2021-86. *Canada Gazette, Part II, Volume 155, Number 10*. Available from: <<https://canadagazette.gc.ca/rp-pr/p2/2021/2021-05-12/html/sor-dors86-eng.html>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- Canadian Government, 2021. Canadian Environmental Protection Act, 1999. Available from: <<https://laws-lois.justice.gc.ca/eng/acts/c-15.31/page-5.html#h-63850>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- Canty, A., Ripley, B., 2022. boot: Bootstrap R (S-Plus) functions. R package version 1.3-28.21.
- Castaldi, G., Cecere, G., Zoli, M., 2021. "Smoke on the beach": on the use of economic vs behavioural policies to reduce environmental pollution by cigarette littering. *Economia Politica* 38, 1025–1048.
- Chen, Y., Awasthi, A.K., Wei, F., Tan, Q., Li, J., 2021. Single-use plastics: production, usage, disposal, and adverse impacts. *Sci. Total Environ.* 752, 141772.
- Chiba, S., Saito, H., Fletcher, R., Yogi, T., Kayo, M., Miyagi, S., Ogido, M., Fujikura, K., 2018. Human footprint in the abyss: 30 year records of deep-sea plastic debris. *Mar. Policy* 96, 204–212.
- Civancik-Uslu, D., Puig, R., Hauschild, M., Fullana-i-Palmer, P., 2019. Life cycle assessment of carrier bags and development of a littering indicator. *Sci. Total Environ.* 685, 621–630.
- Clayton, C.A., Walker, T.R., Bezerra, J.C., Adam, I., 2021. Policy responses to reduce single-use plastic marine pollution in the Caribbean. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 162, 111833.
- Conradi, M., Sánchez-Moyano, J.E., 2022. Toward a sustainable circular economy for cigarette butts, the most common waste worldwide on the coast. *Sci. Total Environ.* 847, 157634.
- Cowger, W., Gray, A., Hapich, H., Osei-Enin, J., Olguin, S., Huynh, B., Nogi, H., Singh, S., Brownlee, S., Ajami, H., 2022. Litter origins, accumulation rates, and hierarchical composition on urban roadsides of the Inland Empire, California. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 17, 015007.
- Cristi, M.A., Holzapfel, C., Nehls, M., De Veer, D., Gonzalez, C., Holtmann, G., Honorato-Zimmer, D., Kiessling, T., Muñoz, A.L., Narváez Reyes, S., Nuñez, P., Sepulveda, J. M., Vásquez, N., Thiel, M., 2020. The rise and demise of plastic shopping bags in Chile – broad and informal coalition supporting ban as a first step to reduce single-use plastics. *Ocean Coast. Manag.* 187, 105079.
- Dittmann, S., Kiessling, T., Kruse, K., Brennecke, D., Knickmeier, K., Parchmann, I., Thiel, M., 2022. How to get citizen science data accepted by the scientific community? Insights from the Plastic Pirates project. In: *Proceedings of Science 124 of the Engaging Citizen Science Conference 2022 (CitSci2022)*, Aarhus University, Denmark.
- EEA, European Environment Agency, 2022. Marine LitterWatch. Available from: <<https://www.eea.europa.eu/themes/water/europes-seas-and-coasts/assessments/marine-litterwatch>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- Elliott, T., Gillie, H., Thomson, A., 2020. European Union's plastic strategy and an impact assessment of the proposed Directive on tackling single-use plastics items. In: *Letcher, T.M. (Ed.), Plastic waste and recycling – Environmental Impact, Social Issues, Prevention, and Solutions*. Academic Press, pp. 601–633.
- Eriksen, M.K., Christiansen, J.D., Daugaard, A.E., Astrup, T.F., 2019. Closing the loop for PET, PE and PP waste from households: Influence of material properties and product design for plastic recycling. *Waste Manag.* 96, 75–85.
- Eriksen, M., Cowger, W., Erdle, L.M., Coffin, S., Villarrubia-Gómez, P., Moore, C.J., Carpenter, E.J., Day, R.H., Thiel, M., Wilcox, C., 2023. A growing plastic smog, now estimated to be over 170 trillion plastic particles afloat in the world's oceans — urgent solutions required. *PLoS One* 18, e0281596.
- EU Directive 2019/904 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 5 June 2019 on the reduction of the impact of certain plastic products on the environment, 2019. Official Journal of the European Union. Available from: <<http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/904/oj>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- European Commission, 2018a. A European Strategy for Plastics in a Circular Economy COM/2018/28. Brussels. Available from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:2df5d1d2-fac7-11e7-b8f5-01aa75ed71a1.0001.02/DOC_1&format=PDF> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- European Commission, 2018b. Assessment of measures to reduce marine litter from single use plastics: final report and annex. Publications Office, 2018. Available from: <<https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2779/500175>> (accessed 7th of March 2023).
- Fox, J., Weisberg, S., 2019. An {R} companion to Applied Regression, third ed. Sage, Thousand Oaks CA. Available from: <<https://socialsciences.mcmaster.ca/jfox/Books/Companion/>> (accessed 2nd of March 2023).
- Geyer, R., Jambeck, J.R., Law, K.L., 2017. Production, use, and fate of all plastics ever made. *Sci. Adv.* 3, e1700782.
- Green, D.S., 2020. Biological and ecological impacts of plastic debris in aquatic ecosystems. In: *Stock, F., Reifferscheid, G., Brennholt, N., Kostianaia, E. (Eds.), Plastics in the Aquatic Environment - Part I*. Springer, Cham, pp. 111–133.
- Groh, K.J., Backhaus, T., Carney-Almroth, B., Geueke, B., Inostroza, P.A., Lennquist, A., Leslie, H.A., Maffini, M., Slunge, D., Trasande, L., Warhurst, A.M., Muncke, J., 2019. Overview of known plastic packaging-associated chemicals and their hazards. *Sci. Total Environ.* 651, 3253–3268.
- Gustavo, J.U., Pereira, G.M., Bond, A.J., Viegas, C.V., Borchardt, M., 2018. Drivers, opportunities and barriers for a retailer in the pursuit of more sustainable packaging redesign. *J. Clean. Prod.* 187, 18–28.
- Hapich, H., Cowger, W., Gray, A., Tangri, N., Hale, T., Magdy, A., Vermilye, A., Yu, W., Ayres, D., Moore, C., Vermilye, J., Singh, S., Haiman, A.N.K., Youngblood, K., Kang, Y., McCauley, M., Lok, T., Moore, S., Baggs, E., Lippiatt, S., Kohler, P., Conley, G., Taing, J., Mock, J., 2022. Trash Taxonomy Tool: harmonizing classification systems used to describe trash in environments. *Microplastics Nanoplastics* 2, 15.
- Harris, L., Liboiron, M., Charron, L., Mather, C., 2021. Using citizen science to evaluate extended producer responsibility policy to reduce marine plastic debris shows no reduction in pollution levels. *Mar. Policy* 123, 104319.
- Heidbreder, L.M., Bablok, I., Drews, S., Menzel, C., 2019. Tackling the plastic problem: a review on perceptions, behaviors, and interventions. *Sci. Total Environ.* 668, 1077–1093.
- Herberz, T., Barlow, C.Y., Finkbeiner, M., 2020. Sustainability assessment of a Single-Use Plastics ban. *Sustainability* 12, 3746.
- Hidalgo-Ruz, V., Thiel, M., 2015. The contribution of citizen scientists to the monitoring of marine litter. In: *Bergmann, M., Gutow, L., Klages, M. (Eds.), Marine Anthropogenic Litter*. Springer, pp. 433–451.
- Hoellein, T.J., Rochman, C.M., 2021. The "plastic cycle": A watershed-scale model of plastic pools and fluxes. *Front. Ecol. Environ.* 19, 176–183.
- Hoge, S., Brandão, M., 2020. Straw wars – a consequential saga: The life cycle climate change consequences of replacing plastic with paper. In: *Brandão, M., Lazarevic, D., Finnveden, G. (Eds.), Handbook of the Circular Economy*. Edward Elgar Publishing, pp. 410–424.
- Khedr, S., Rehdanz, K., Brouwer, R., van Beukering, P., Dijkstra, H., Duijndam, S., Okoli, I.C., 2023. Public preferences for marine plastic litter management across Europe. *Ecol. Econ.* 204, 107609.
- Kiessling, T., Knickmeier, K., Kruse, K., Brennecke, D., Nauendorf, A., Thiel, M., 2019. Plastic Pirates sample litter at rivers in Germany – riverside litter and litter sources estimated by schoolchildren. *Environ. Pollut.* 245, 545–557.
- Kiessling, T., Knickmeier, K., Kruse, K., Gatta-Rosemary, M., Nauendorf, A., Brennecke, D., Thiel, L., Wichels, A., Parchmann, I., Körtzinger, A., Thiel, M., 2021. Schoolchildren discover hotspots of floating plastic litter in rivers using a large-scale collaborative approach. *Sci. Total Environ.* 789, 147849.
- Knoblauch, D., Mederake, L., Stein, U., 2018. Developing countries in the lead – what drives the diffusion of plastic bag policies? *Sustainability* 10, 1994.
- Kühn, S., van Franeker, J.A., 2020. Quantitative overview of marine debris ingested by marine megafauna. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 151, 110858.
- Larrington-Spencer, H., Fenney, D., Middlemiss, L., Kosanic, A., 2021. Disabled environmentalisms. In: *Bell, K. (Ed.), Diversity and Inclusion in Environmentalism*. Routledge, pp. 15–33.
- Lau, W.W., Shiran, Y., Bailey, R.M., Cook, E., Stuchtey, M.R., Koskella, J., Velis, C.A., Godfrey, L., Boucher, J., Murphy, M.B., Thompson, R.C., Jankowska, E., Castillo, A. C., Pilditch, T.D., Dixon, B., Koerselman, L., Kosior, E., Favoino, E., Guterber, J., Baulch, S., Atreya, M.E., Fischer, D., He, K.K., Petit, M.M., Sumaila, U.R., Neil, E., Bernhofen, M.V., Lawrence, K., Palardy, J.E., 2020. Evaluating scenarios toward zero plastic pollution. *Science* 369, 1455–1461.
- Lechner, A., 2020. "Down by the River": (Micro-)Plastic pollution of running freshwaters with special emphasis on the Austrian Danube. In: *Streit-Bianchi, M., Cimadevila, M., Trettnak, W. (Eds.), Mare Plasticum - The Plastic Sea*. Springer, Cham, pp. 141–185.
- Mitchell, C., Quaglino, M.C., Posner, V.M., Arranz, S.E., Sciara, A.A., 2021. Quantification and composition analysis of plastic pollution in riverine beaches of the lower Paraná River, Argentina. *Environ. Sci. Pollut. Res.* 28, 16140–16151.
- Morales-Caselles, C., Viejo, J., Martí, E., González-Fernández, D., Pragnell-Raasch, H., González-Gordillo, J.I., Montero, E., Arroyo, G.M., Hanke, G., Salvo, V.S., Basurko, O.C., Mallos, N., Lebreton, L., Echevarría, F., van Emmerik, T., Duarte, C. M., Gálvez, J.A., van Sebille, E., Galgani, F., García, C.M., Ross, P.S., Bartual, A., Ioakeimidis, C., Markalain, G., Isobe, A., Cózar, A., 2021. An inshore-offshore

- sorting system revealed from global classification of ocean litter. *Nat. Sustainability* 4, 484–493.
- Morritt, D., Stefanoudis, P.V., Pearce, D., Crimmen, O.A., Clark, P.F., 2014. Plastic in the Thames: a river runs through it. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 78, 196–200.
- Nelms, S.E., Coombes, C., Foster, L.C., Galloway, T.S., Godley, B.J., Lindeque, P.K., Witt, M.J., 2017. Marine anthropogenic litter on British beaches: a 10-year nationwide assessment using citizen science data. *Sci. Total Environ.* 579, 1399–1409.
- Nielsen, T.D., Holmberg, K., Strippel, J., 2019. Need a bag? A review of public policies on plastic carrier bags—Where, how and to what effect? *Waste Manag.* 87, 428–440.
- Ocean Conservancy, 2022. TIDES – Trash Information and Data for Education and Solutions. Available from: <<https://www.coastalcleanupdata.org/reports/>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- OSPAR Commission, 2010. Guideline for Monitoring Marine Litter on the Beaches in the OSPAR Maritime Area. OSPAR Commission, London.
- Parthasarathy, A., Tyler, A.C., Hoffman, M.J., Savka, M.A., Hudson, A.O., 2019. Is plastic pollution in aquatic and terrestrial environments a driver for the transmission of pathogens and the evolution of antibiotic resistance? *Environ. Sci. Tech.* 53, 1744–1745.
- Penca, J., 2018. European Plastics Strategy: What promise for global marine litter? *Mar. Policy* 97, 197–201.
- Qiu, R., Song, Y., Zhang, X., Xie, B., He, D. (2020). Microplastics in urban environments: sources, pathways, and distribution. In: He, D., Luo, Y. (Eds.), *Microplastics in Terrestrial Environments*. Springer, pp. 41–61.
- R Core Team, 2020. R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. Available from: <<https://www.R-project.org/>> (accessed 2nd of March 2023).
- Rech, S., Macaya-Caquilpán, V., Pantoja, J.F., Rivadeneira, M.M., Madariaga, D.J., Thiel, M., 2014. Rivers as a source of marine litter – a study from the SE Pacific. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 82, 66–75.
- RStudio Team, 2022. RStudio: Integrated Development Environment for R. RStudio, PBC, Boston, MA. Available from: <<http://www.rstudio.com/>> (accessed 2nd of March 2023).
- Rubio, S., Ramos, T.R.P., Leitão, M.M.R., Barbosa-Povoa, A.P., 2019. Effectiveness of extended producer responsibility policies implementation: the case of Portuguese and Spanish packaging waste systems. *J. Clean. Prod.* 210, 217–230.
- Schneider, F., Kunz, A., Hu, C.S., Yen, N., Lin, H.T., 2021. Rapid-survey methodology to assess litter volumes along large river systems – a case study of the Tamsui River in Taiwan. *Sustainability* 13, 8765.
- Schnurr, R.E.J., Alboiu, V., Chaudhary, M., Corbett, R.A., Quanz, M.E., Sankar, K., Srain, H.S., Thavarajah, V., Xanthos, D., Walker, T.R., 2018. Reducing marine pollution from single-use plastics (SUPs): a review. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 137, 157–171.
- Schöneich-Argent, R.I., Hillmann, F., Cordes, D., Wansing, R.A.D., Merder, J., Freund, J. A., Freund, H., 2019. Wind, waves, tides, and human error? – Influences on litter abundance and composition on German North Sea coastlines: an exploratory analysis. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 146, 155–172.
- Schöneich-Argent, R.I., Dau, K., Freund, H., 2020. Wasting the North Sea? – A field-based assessment of anthropogenic macrolitter loads and emission rates of three German tributaries. *Environ. Pollut.* 263, 114367.
- Taylor, R.L., 2019. Bag leakage: The effect of disposable carryout bag regulations on unregulated bags. *J. Environ. Econ. Manag.* 93, 254–271.
- Taylor, R.L., Villas-Boas, S.B., 2016. Bans vs. fees: disposable carryout bag policies and bag usage. *Appl. Econ. Perspect. Policy* 38, 351–372.
- van Emmerik, T., Mellink, Y., Hauk, R., Waldschläger, K., Schreyers, L., 2022. Rivers as plastic reservoirs. *Frontiers in Water* 3, 1–8.
- van Sebille, E., Aliani, S., Law, K.L., Maximenko, N., Alsina, J.M., Bagaev, A., Bergmann, M., Chapron, B., Chubarenko, I., Cózar, A., Delandmeter, P., Egger, M., Fox-Kemper, B., Garaba, S.P., Goddijn-Murphy, L., Hardesty, B.D., Hoffman, M.J., Isobe, A., Jongedijk, C.E., Kaandorp, M.L.A., Khatmullina, L., Koelmans, A.A., Kukulka, T., Laufkötter, C., Lebreton, L., Lobelle, D., Maes, C., Martinez-Vincente, V., Morales Maqueda, M.A., Poulain-Zarcos, M., Rodríguez, E., Ryan, P.G., Shanks, A.L., Shim, W.J., Suaria, G., Thiel, M., van den Bremer, T.S., Wichmann, D., 2020. The physical oceanography of the transport of floating marine debris. *Environ. Res. Lett.* 15, 023003.
- Vlachogianni, T., Fortibuoni, T., Ronchi, F., Zerì, C., Mazziotti, C., Tutman, P., Vrežič, D.B., Palatinus, A., Trdan, S., Peterlin, M., Mandić, M., Markovic, O., Prvan, M., Kaberi, H., Prevenios, M., Kolutari, J., Kroqi, G., Fusco, M., Kalampokis, E., Scoullou, M., 2018. Marine litter on the beaches of the Adriatic and Ionian Seas: an assessment of their abundance, composition and sources. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 131, 745–756.
- Wagner, T.P., 2017. Reducing single-use plastic shopping bags in the USA. *Waste Manag.* 70, 3–12.
- Wagner, T.P., 2020. Policy instruments to reduce consumption of expanded polystyrene food service ware in the USA. *Detritus* 9, 11.
- Walker, T.R., 2021. Plastic industry plan to sue the Canadian federal government for listing plastic as toxic may increase plastic marine pollution. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 169, 112583.
- Watkins, E., Gionfra, S., Schweitzer, J.-P., Pantzar, M., Janssens, C., & ten Brink, P., 2017. EPR in the EU Plastics Strategy and the Circular Economy: a focus on plastic packaging. Institute for European Environmental Policy. Available from: <<https://ieep.eu/uploads/articles/attachments/95369718-a733-473b-aa6b-153c1341f581/EPR%20and%20plastics%20report%20IEEP%2009%20Nov%202017%20final.pdf>> (accessed 10th of October 2022).
- Xanthos, D., Walker, T.R., 2017. International policies to reduce plastic marine pollution from single-use plastics (plastic bags and microbeads): a review. *Mar. Pollut. Bull.* 118 (1–2), 17–26.
- Zettler, E.R., Takada, H., Monteleone, B., Mallos, N., Eriksen, M., Amaral-Zettler, L.A., 2017. Incorporating citizen science to study plastics in the environment. *Anal. Methods* 9, 1392–1403.
- Zhou, G., Gu, Y., Wu, Y., Gong, Y., Mu, X., Han, H., Chang, T., 2020. A systematic review of the deposit-refund system for beverage packaging: operating mode, key parameter and development trend. *J. Clean. Prod.* 251, 119660.